

Original Research

Factors Affecting Employee Retention and Logistic Performance: Evidence from NGO Sector in Northern Area of Bangladesh

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Abstract

It is conceivable to question why highly educated and competent workers are permitted to leave their employment. The determination of this paper is to identify the important issues prompting worker retaining in the northern Bangladesh NGO sector and to examine how staff retention impacts on logistic performance. Some of the things that are looked at in this study as retention drivers are economic stability, psychological security, connections with coworkers, and self-actualization. With a simple random sampling method and a questionnaire, the employees are polled to get the important information. We selected Rajshahi, Bogra, Natore, and Kushtia as well as four NGOs from each district for the random sample. Each NGO conducted ten worker interviews for data collection. The total number of samples is 160. SEM-SPLS examines data, evaluates the research model and hypotheses, and tests the study model and hypotheses. There are economic, psychological, interpersonal, and self-actualization aspects of employee retention. The paper covers the hypothetical and applied ramifications of the inquiry.

Keywords: Employee retention, NGO, Organizational performance, Bangladesh.

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Introduction

Every firm depends on its ability to recruit, retain, and reward competent and productive employees. Keeping qualified employees is a critical source of competitive advantage for every company. When a business makes an effort to keep its employees, it faces a number of challenges (Barney 1991; Pettman 1975; Wernerfelt 1984). Individuals who perform poorly and produce little are typically encouraged to quit their jobs, while companies want to keep hold of employees who are able to think beyond the box. If it were possible to quantify it, businesses would hire and retain workers who had a stronger positive influence on the company's value and profits. Considering the cost of recruiting and training a new worker, it is preferable to keep a productive worker on staff rather than replace them. According to Gering and Conner (2002), any firm must maintain a productive staff. This is because a company cannot maximize the growth of its human capital if it cannot retain its employees. Several research (Alshurideh 2017, Alshurideh et al. 2017, Alshurideh 2016a,b,c,d; Kurdi et al. 2020) have investigated client retention and the extent to which it is advantageous for firms (Alshurideh, 2016a). This point of view supports the idea that employees are crucial to a company's success. In spite of this, there is a dearth of studies examining the factors that contribute to employee loyalty and turn them into an organization's most valuable resource. The financial sector is essential to any country's economy, both directly and indirectly. Furthermore, in the banking business, turnover rates are on the rise, particularly among dissatisfied employees, and the propensity to leave the firm is growing (Schuler & Jackson 2006). This becomes a serious problem for the business and a costly software program if key personnel are leaving. Not to mention the time and money required to train a new hire.

Therefore, it is important to investigate the issues that have an important impact on employee's retention in the NGO sector in Bangladesh. Employee retention may be greatly influenced by a variety of elements, such as job security, social support, wisdom of purpose, and overall happiness. The purpose for this research was to discover what keeps individuals with commercial NGOs in northern Bangladesh. The administration of non-governmental organizations is beginning to place a larger emphasis on retention strategies, as these plans target the organization's most important asset: its employees. The research investigates these approaches for retaining knowledge in greater depth. Focus is given on how employee retention influences institutional performance in their management environment and in growing markets, as well as how psychological work safety, economic work safety, interaction with others, and self-satisfaction influence employee retention. The industry of nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) might be a significant factor in Bangladesh's social endeavors. Despite this, Bangladesh's flourishing non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and microcredit distribution businesses continued to develop while being closely watched. There are now close to 150 notable NGOs functioning in the region. Researchers such as Oladapo (2014) have investigated the issue in order to comprehend what talent management entails and how leaders may ensure they have the tools and knowledge to study their team in order to identify the most talented individuals. To retain employees, businesses must develop ties with them on several levels, including financially, emotionally, and socially.

Rationale of the study and objectives

This study's major purpose is to raise the Bangladeshi NGO community's awareness of the need of maintaining one of their most valuable resources: their workforce (Vasquez 2014). This study underwrites to the current body of knowledge on the subject of employee retention by exploring the problems of establishing a new

Theoretical framework based on past research in the banking industry. Most research have concentrated on client retention (Alshurideh 2013; Alshurideh, Masa'deh, and Al Kurdi 2012; Ashurideh 2010); therefore, this research could help fill knowledge and understanding gaps about the value of retaining employees in the non-governmental organization (NGO) sector and contribute to the growth of the sector. This study is significant because it attempts to develop a novel approach to staff retention. In the future, the findings of this study may be utilized to explain what inspires employees to remain with a firm. Consequently, this investigation is crucial. Additionally, it might influence the decision-making process of those who work for banks and other financial organizations. This is significant since a significant number of employees in this field have switched careers in recent years. Taking action to address this issue provides firms with the opportunity to generate innovative strategies for increasing employee retention. Therefore, the study contributes to the economic sector's continued growth and stability by enhancing their economic standing. This is accomplished through reducing the expenses associated with recruiting, employing, and training new personnel, as well as the costs associated with losing individuals with specialized expertise. Also, the research is one of the first to examine the difficulty of retaining workers in one of the rising sectors by developing a theoretical model and statistically evaluating it. This was made possible by the study. This establishes the foundation for future studies on how to retain staff in the banking business. These findings should inspire academics to conduct further research on this area, particularly for the benefit of companies that wish to retain their staff. Companies must recognize and understand that not all of their workers are loyal or devoted to the organization for which they work. Some employees remain with a company because they fear leaving their positions or work teams (Shapiro and Kirkman, 1999), they feel connected to the company's culture, or they are unable to obtain other employment. According to Hafeez, Malak, and Zhang (2007) and Alshurideh et al., people are a company's most valuable asset since they impact its total profitability (2020). Alzoubi et al. (2020) and Alshurideh (2019) discovered that retaining workers helps retain consumers, reduces operating expenses, and reduces the cost of acquiring and training new employees. This clarifies the circumstances. This study investigates the relationship between psychological, physiological, relational, and self-actualizing aspects and employee retention.

Literature Review

Economic security and employee retention

The notion of security is centered on anticipating and explaining a range of activities done to avoid or mitigate the effects of malevolent threats to people's lives or property. All points of contact with national security organizations, including the military and police, are included in the security sector. The "security economy" is the

Term we will use to describe these efforts to counteract economic uncertainty, its sources, and its impacts (OECD 2004). The infrastructure for basic necessities, which covers areas like health care, education, housing, information, social protection, and stable job, shapes it. Maintaining aspects connected to work security can help you achieve financial stability (International Labor Organisation 2004). Workers in any country or sector are less inclined to relocate to another nation or industry or search for new employment when they feel financially secure. As Singh (2012) demonstrates, both employee retention and long-term economic sustainability are possible as long as employees possess the required skills. Slow economic growth is seen in countries like Greece and Spain when unemployment rates are high (Fountoulakis 2014). It is possible to propose the following consequences of economic security on employee retention based on this definition:

H₁: Employees' Economic security influences employees' retention, positively.

Mental satisfaction and employee retention

In Maslow's theory of motivation, which is based on the notion of a hierarchy of human needs, a stable state of mind is seen as the first and most fundamental level. This variable is based on the capacity of individuals to maintain a regular and normal state of their essential life demands. It comprises the material requirements for human existence, such as food, water, the ability to breathe, shelter, etc (Adair 2006). As a result of having a work that will be there for a while, employees with job security usually enjoy a steady, regular lifestyle and are able to effectively meet their requirements and expectations. Strong psychological sustainability contributes to strong overall sustainability, which boosts worker gratification and presentation. Mental security in the commercial segment may be characterized as the provision of a proper working environment and the receipt of enough financial recompense. If these elements are lacking, employees will be compelled to seek work elsewhere in order to meet their psychological wants (Hanif, Khalid & Khan 2013). On the basis of this conception of psychological security, the following may be said about the relationship between psychological safety and employee retention:

H₂: Employees' mental satisfaction influences employees' retention, positively.

Relationship with other colleague and employee retention

A person's behavior and performance may be anticipated and explained using McClelland's theory of needs. These needs have been categorized as the need for connections, the desire for power, and the need for success. Typical aspects of the need for affiliation include the desire to become more socially oriented, to spend more time with friends and coworkers, to be liked, and to spend more time in social relationships and workgroups. Additionally, it encourages teamwork in circumstances when collaboration and reciprocity are crucial (Yamaguchi 2003). A connection may be made in the banking industry if a worker is extroverted, concerned with establishing and maintaining interpersonal relationships, and willing to work in a collaborative environment. In addition, the applicant must be seeking work in a cooperative

environment. On the basis of an understanding of association, the following may be expressed as the effect of employee connection on employee retention:

H₃: Employee relationship with other influences employee retention, positively.

Self-realization and employee retention

Self-realization is a person's ability to achieve his or her own possible; it differs. A parent who can provide for his family may be self-aware. After completing a job-related research project, a scientist may gain self-awareness (McLeod 2007). Self-actualization requires going beyond homeostasis, improving creativity, and having "peak experiences." These things help people reach their full potential. When people reach their maximum potential, they're more productive and creative (Maddi 1996). Self-realization is an extraordinary characteristic, not a regular manner of activity. Self-realized persons are readily distinguishable from the bulk of people (Soni and Soni 2016). Business self-actualization is realizing one's full potential and fulfilling one's full potential as an employee. This may happen when leaders and management help an employee become more motivated and productive (Hanif et al. 2013). Self-realization may have the following effects on employee retention, based on what we know about it:

H₄: Employee self-realization influences employee retention, definitely.

Employee retention

The retaining of employees affects the majority of corporate divisions and is a critical topic for business management. All managers and stakeholders must plan for employee retention and investigate its impact on behavior and output (Mohanty, 2009). Employer retention entails retaining desirable personnel to achieve business objectives (Frank, Finnegan & Taylor 2004). Turnover refers to a company employee's voluntary departure. Prior study on employee retention centered on senior employees for ethical concerns (Calo 2008). According to one research, employee retention has long influenced professional commitment, employee happiness, employee motivation, and employee behavior (Davis 2013). According to the survey, employee retention is key. Absenteeism, early retirement, and staff turnover are linked to job dissatisfaction (Saari & Judge 2004). Irshad and Afridi said HRM is key to monitoring and regulating workforce retention (2011). First, ensure a candidate's skills match the job description. "Compensation" is key to attracting and retaining employees. This is especially true for extraordinary performers or people. Organizations appreciate these traits because they result from employee development and orientation. The term rewards refers to all of the monetary and non-monetary benefits given to employees for successful work performance. The company is required under training and career development" to teach its employees how to enhance future sales. The sixth component, "Career advancement 3984 opportunities," entails balancing employee expectations and corporate needs. The sixth factor, "supervisor support," refers to the employee's positive working connection with the supervisor. A poor connection decreases the probability that an employee will remain. The seventh factor, "work environment," influences the likelihood that individuals will work for and remain with firms where they feel valued and can be productive. Organizational justice refers to the company's ethical treatment of its employees. Since recruiting suitable

employees is essential to the success of any business, employee retention is the top priority. Retention is more crucial than recruitment since the firm must spend more on training the new employee, and replacing an old worker may cost twofold as much as employing a new one (Alshurideh 2014, 2019; Irshad & Afridi 2007). We will now examine how employee retention impacts performance.

Logistic performance in Job

The impact of employee retention on the achievement of a task is one of the most important issues that may be discussed. AlDamoe, Yazam, and Ahmid's (2012) research on human resource management methods centered on those associated with the effect of employee retention on task completion. The study's findings reveal that staff retention moderated these types of relationships and effects across all firms. This corroborates the findings of Paul and Anantharaman (2003), who discovered that human resource management strategies, such as staff productivity and employee retention, have an effect on task completion and financial success. This outcome corresponds to theirs. Numerous research have found a correlation between worker retention and performance (Gberevbie, 2010, Markos, & Sridevi, 2010), worker engagement and retention (Markos, & Sridevi, 2010), worker behavior and task completion (Cascio, 2006), and worker behavior and retention (Gberevbie 2010). (Gberevbie 2010). (2006) (2010) (2013) (2013) Using this definition of work completion, staff retention has the following effects on task performance:

H₅: Employee retention influences logistic performance in job, positively.

Theoretical Background

This study aims to uncover the most influential elements that lead to employee retention in the nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) sector in Bangladesh. Our model is based on a meta-analysis of several previous studies with high impact and significant ties to the current topic. As seen in Figure 1, the four primary factors that influence employee retention are economic stability, psychological security, contact with others, and self-actualization. It was expected that these factors would influence and encourage employee retention, which would have a ripple impact on company outcomes.

Fig. 1. The hypothetical model

Hypotheses and functional definitions

The study was intended to investigate a variety of variables that motivate employees to remain with NGOs. On the basis of the study model depicted in Figure 1, the following assumptions were formulated:

H₁: Employee Economic security favorably promotes employee retention.

H₂: Employee mental security favorably promotes employee retention.

H₃: Employee relationship with others influences employee retention positively.

H₄: Employee self-realization influences employee retention positively.

H₅: Employee retention influences logistic performance effectively positively.

This study focused on clarifying several ideas. If a person has the right talents, he or she can preserve the company's financial stability. Employees seek jobs that suit their psychological demands; having a nice work environment and competitive pay helps create mental stability at work. Social needs emerge organically when people spend more time with coworkers and in groups. Self-actualization may occur in company when leaders and managers assist individuals increase motivation and output, recognizing the happiness that comes from using one's talents and abilities.

Research Methodology

This study used a quantitative technique and a validated questionnaire to obtain primary data needed to analyze employee retention in the Northern area of Bangladesh's NGO sector. Five commercial NGOs in the northern portion of Bangladesh were sampled randomly for basic data. Although the questionnaire was randomly distributed to four NGOs, ASA, BRAC, GM Bank, and TMSS, only 160 were valid for analysis. Individually delivered survey questionnaires led to an 82% response rate. Respondents gave their opinions on the research using a Likert scale ranging from highly agreeing to strongly rejecting. Participants in the research sample rated the study structures to determine which factor influenced their ability to recall the content. Men made up 71% of the sample and women 29%. 26% of survey respondents had a high school education, 57% a bachelors, and 17% a postgraduate degree. 45% of participants had worked for the same employer for less than three years, 32% for less than five, and 23% for more than five.

Data Analysis

Several statistical techniques, including Factor Loading (FL), Cronbach's Alpha, CR and AVE, and R², were used to examine the study model and build items in this work. According to the FL data, Table 1 reveals that for each construct, four items were suitable for data collection. All of the items with FL values between 0.74 and 0.877 were declared appropriate for use. Cronbach's Alpha ratings for study constructs varied from 0.771 to 0.834 and were all more than 70%. All CR values were over 70%, and all AVE values were over 50%. According to Hair et al. (2017) and other statistical measures, the results

showed that the convergent validity and reliability for each research element and the study model's measurements met statistical standards (Alshurideh et al. 2020; Alzoubi et al. 2020; Kurdi 2016).

Table. 1 Convergent validity results

Constructs	Items	Factor loading	Cronbach`s Alpha	CR	AVE
Economic Security	ES-1	0.86	0.8	0.79	0.7
	ES-2	0.83			
	ES-3	0.81			
	ES-4	0.82			
Mental security	MS-1	0.76	0.78	0.72	0.76
	MS-2	0.79			
	MS-3	0.74			
	MS-4	0.81			
Relationship with others	RS-1	0.82	0.86	0.78	0.69
	RS-2	0.84			
	RS-3	0.81			
	RS-4	0.83			
Self- Realization	SR-1	0.74	0.77	0.73	0.63
	SR-2	0.72			
	SR-3	0.79			
	SR-4	0.76			
Employee retention	ER-1	0.79	0.84	0.81	0.59
	ER-2	0.71			
	ER-3	0.77			
	ER-4	0.87			
Task achievement	TA-1	0.80	0.85	0.76	0.69
	TA-2	0.86			
	TA-3	0.87			
	TA-4	0.83			

Acceptable values (Factor loading, Cronbach`s Alpha, composite reliability ≥ 0.70 & AVE > 0.5)

In this study, a number of statistical approaches, including Factor Loading (FL), Cronbach's Alpha, CR, AVE, and R2, were utilized to evaluate the study model and construct items. Table 1 demonstrates, based on the FL data that for each construct, there were four eligible questions that could be utilized to gather the main data. The FL values of each item were between 0.71 and 0.87, indicating that they were all suitable for usage. Cronbach's Alpha scores for the study's constructs varied between 0.77 and 0.85, indicating that they all above 70%. The range of CR values was 0.72 to 0.81, which was usually greater than 70%. AVE values were between 0.59 and 0.76, usually over 50%. Numerous statistical measures that Hair et al. (2017) defined and compared to others (Alshurideh et al. 2020; Alzoubi et al. 2020; Kurdi 2016) demonstrated that each research element and the study model measurements fulfilled statistical criteria.

Table 2. Correlation Matrix

	Economic Security	Mental Security	Relationship	Self-realization	Employee retention
Economic Security	0.71				
Mental Security	0.56	0.78			
Relationship	0.42	0.49	0.64		
Self-realization	0.39	0.57	0.52	0.72	
Employee retention	0.48	0.54	0.43	0.51	0.77

Table 2 shows the correlation and cross-loading coefficients. Each construct's correlation with itself was higher than with the others. Correlations ranged from 0.39 to 0.77. This showed a favorable link between researches constructs.

Table: 3 the value of R²

Constructs	R ²	Results
Employee Retention Drivers	0.79	High

The coefficient of determination (R²) was the most important factor in the entire analysis of the constructed model. Chin (1998) and Liu, Liao, and Peng (2005) consider a value to be high if it exceeds 60 percent. As shown in Table 3, as a result, the model demonstrated a high capacity for describing the investigated events, and its prediction capacity was 72.1%.

Table: 4 Structural Model hypothesis analysis

H	Relationship	Path	t-value	p-value	Direction	Decision
H1	ES -> ER	.14	9.7	.001	+ Positive	Maintained
H2	MS -> ER	.52	9.8	.004	+ Positive	Maintained
H3	RS -> ER	.16	10.57	.05	+ Positive	Maintained
H4	SR -> ER	.19	4.25	.03	+ Positive	Maintained
H5	ER -> TA	.11	7.36	.04	+ Positive	Maintained

The route analysis was utilized to assess and validate the hypotheses of the investigation. SEM-SPLS was used to validate the theorized connection between the research variables. Table 4 presents the results of the suggested hypothesis's route analysis. Evidently, all hypothesized associations were evaluated and shown to be statistically significant. The data analysis confirmed the hypotheses H1, H2, H2, H4, and

H5 as follows: (= 0.14, P0.002) for the first factor, (= 0.52, P0.004) for the second factor, (= 0.16, P0.000), (= 0.19, P0.001) for the third component, and (= 0.11, P0.005) for the last factor. Table 4 offers an overview of the results of the hypothesis testing.

Findings and discussion

According to respondents, personal growth had the least impact on whether or not they remained with their current business. This study provides support for the notion that psychological well-being is a prerequisite for employment in any company, but is especially important in businesses that place a premium on cooperation (Rasmussen & Jeppesen 2006).

Both the unemployment rate and increased staff turnover hinder the expansion of the national economy. According to Vasquez's (2014) research, it may be able to increase employee retention by upgrading the workplace in a variety of ways, such as by offering incentive and reward programs and strong management support. Salman, Ahmad, and Matin's (2014) examination of worker retention in the Pakistani banking industry in Karachi provides more support. Researchers concluded that a bank's performance was significantly dependent on employee retention. Increasing worker turnover and its negative impact on banking sector productivity inhibited economic growth. Instead of resigning themselves to the inevitable loss of their most valuable personnel, managers in the banking industry can implement strategies to encourage and reward their best workers to remain. Consequently, maintaining a stable economy is necessary for retaining employees, and maintaining a stable economy is necessary for retaining workers. Several scholars, including Ramlall, have confirmed this association (2004). The results validated the second hypothesis, which postulated a connection between psychological security and staff retention (value of 0.423 and P value of 0.004). These researchers discovered that elements outside financial stability, such as employees' emotional well-being, had a substantial impact in determining whether they would remain with a company. They predicted that if upper management paid more attention to these concerns, turnover rates would fall. In addition, Nowack and Learning (2008) argued that maintaining a psychologically healthy workplace was essential for retaining competent workers. Fortunately, there are a number of methods to meet these needs, including enhancing employee participation and cultivating strong social and emotional capabilities. Sandhya and Kumar's (2011) findings showed the relevance of providing employees with a safe and welcoming environment if firms wish to enhance retention rates. The results validated the third hypothesis, which postulated that interpersonal ties influenced employee retention (value of 0.132 and P-value of 0.000). Given the lack of research on the issue, it is hard to overestimate the significance of this revelation. According to professionals such as Kyndt et al. (2009), respect, encouragement, and the opportunity to be heard—particularly from direct supervisors—are essential for retaining competent and talented employees. For top talent to prosper, a more convivial workplace was also essential. Therefore, it is essential to focus on the particular abilities of each individual. Lee and Way elaborated on the extent to which individual characteristics might influence job satisfaction and retention in the hospitality industry (2010). Presumably, high-performing employees should be retained since they are more likely to be loyal to the company and their coworkers, have a positive attitude on consumers, and value teamwork. The results of the study supported the fourth hypothesis, which posited that allowing workers to

pursue their own objectives at work would boost retention rates ($= 0.182$, $P 0.001$) Some businesses took advantage of every chance to educate their personnel, laying the groundwork for future success and overcoming any difficulties that arose (Alshurideh 2019; Alzoubi et al. 2020). Ghannajeh, et al. (2015); Obeidat, Alshurideh, Al Dweeri, and Masa'deh (n.d.); Alshurideh, Ghannajeh, and Masa'deh (2019); (2019). Data (value of 0.152 and P-value of 0.005) supporting the fifth hypothesis that employee retention has an impact on business success. When the antecedent employee retention variables were appropriately considered in addition to the previously evaluated independent factors, employees remained in their positions longer than normal. Keeping key staff, particularly those with specialized experience, enhanced job productivity (Alshraideh, Al-Lozi & Alshurideh 2017; Alshurideh, Alhadid & Al Kurdi 2015; Brayfield & Crockett 1955). When employees' physical and emotional safety is addressed and their social and working environments are well-maintained, they are more likely to be satisfied, feel proud of themselves, have strong relationships with others, and achieve their full potential (Alshurideh et al. 2015; Zu'bi et al. As a consequence, the company is typically able to retain its best staff, which increases its overall performance. 9 - In conclusion In this study, we examined the effectiveness of four potential motivators: psychological, monetary, interpersonal, and self-actualization. The context for this study was the Jordanian commercial banking industry, one of the region's developing economies. Employee retention is increased when employees appreciate their jobs, coworkers, supervisors, and even the clients they serve (Alshurideh et al., 2020; Alzoubi et al. 2020). Those in positions of control and responsibility should give this matter considerable consideration. Service providers must retain their best and brightest personnel in order to run a profitable business and offer a great work environment for their clients (Alshurideh et al. 2015; ELSamen and Alshurideh 2012). A pleasant workplace enables employees to engage positively with coworkers, bosses, and customers (Alshurideh et al., 2015; Alshurideh, Al Kurdi, Abumari & Salloum, 2018; Ammari, Al Kurdi, Alshurideh & Alrowwad, 2017). If they believe their superiors value, accept, and encourage them to express their thoughts and feelings, satisfied employees are more likely to remain with the same company for a long time (Alshurideh, Shaltoni and Hijawi, 2014; Alshurideh, 2016; Ammari, Al Kurdi, Alshurideh & Alrowwad, 2017). When employees feel valued and appreciated, they are more likely to undertake tough assignments, test out fresh approaches, and be comfortable working in environments where they frequently need to raise their voices to be heard by someone less than one meter away. When employees feel valued at work, they are more likely to perceive issues as chances for advancement rather than hurdles. Moreover, individuals develop faith in their talents and self-assurance in their capacity to accomplish occupations that will challenge, inspire, and extend them. Management must make a concerted effort to identify and provide all opportunities for people to acquire new skills. As a consequence, employees felt in control of their job and confident in their capacity to execute everyday chores efficiently. Additionally, they indicated that the benefits of achievement surpassed the costs of failure. It is ultimately the job of the business to not only locate, hire, and retain the finest and brightest personnel, but also to ensure that they remain with the company. Companies get a competitive advantage by retaining their finest staff, as they are the most committed to the project at hand (Balakrishnan, 2014). In light of this study's findings, senior management should develop a strategic strategy to retain their most qualified and competent staff.

Conclusion

In this study, we examined the effectiveness of four potential motivators: psychological, monetary, interpersonal, and self-actualization. The context for this study was the Jordanian commercial banking industry, one of the region's developing economies. Employee retention is increased when employees appreciate their jobs, coworkers, supervisors, and even the clients they serve (Alshurideh et al., 2020; Alzoubi et al. 2020). Those in positions of authority and responsibility should pay great attention to this matter. Service providers must retain their best and brightest personnel in order to run a profitable business and offer a great work environment for their clients (Alshurideh et al. 2015; ELSamen and Alshurideh 2012). A cheerful workplace encourages employees to connect positively with coworkers, bosses, and customers (Alshurideh et al., 2015; Alshurideh, Al Kurdi, Abumari & Salloum, 2018; Ammari, Al Kurdi, Alshurideh & Alrowwad, 2017). Compared to dissatisfied workers, delighted employees are more likely to stay with the same business if they believe their superiors respect, accept, and encourage them to voice their thoughts and feelings (Alshurideh, Shaltoni and Hijawi, 2014; Alshurideh, 2016; Ammari, Al Kurdi, Alshurideh & Alrowwad, 2017). When employees feel valued and appreciated, they are more likely to undertake tough assignments, test out fresh approaches, and be comfortable working in environments where they frequently need to raise their voices to be heard by someone less than one meter away. When employees feel valued at work, they are more likely to perceive issues as chances for advancement rather than hurdles. Moreover, individuals develop faith in their talents and self-assurance in their capacity to accomplish occupations that will challenge, inspire, and extend them. Management must make a concerted effort to identify and provide all opportunities for people to acquire new skills. As a consequence, employees felt in control of their job and confident in their capacity to execute everyday chores efficiently. Additionally, they indicated that the benefits of achievement surpassed the costs of failure. It is ultimately the job of the business to not only locate, hire, and retain the finest and brightest personnel, but also to ensure that they remain with the company. Companies get a competitive advantage by retaining their finest staff, as they are the most committed to the project at hand (Balakrishnan, 2014). In light of this study's findings, senior organization should develop a strategic strategy to retain their most qualified and competent staff.

Study theoretical and practical implications

The study findings have led to a number of hypothetical and applied inferences that may be used to tackle a range of employee retention issues. To begin with, more study and analysis are required to determine how employees in expanding areas feel about their jobs. Managers should be concerned with the psychological issues their employees encounter, as well as the ways in which their psychological states develop and remain stable through time. Second, the majority of companies were concerned about the annual assessment forms and reports they gave to their employees. These performance metrics were based on items that could be seen and handled, but did not take psychological symptoms into consideration. There is an urgent demand for new assessment pointers that are related to emotional assessment instruments, particularly among large-scale employers. Thirdly, respondents believed that economic and physical aspects of the work were significant determinants of employee retention. Fourth, more study must be

conducted on workplace-related issues, such as how well individuals understand their jobs, how noisy their jobs are, how large their offices are, how healthy their work surroundings are, how safe their jobs are, and how dangerous their jobs are. Fifth, additional study is required to examine the various types of employment and how people perceive their duties. Managers should research and keep an eye on ways to assist workers become more self-aware and remain with the firm, keeping in mind how difficult some activities are and how hard people strive to do everyday chores that are viewed as difficult. They should also consider how to encourage employees' creativity in their daily activities. There are several factors that must be investigated and recorded in order for workers to learn about themselves and remain with the organization.

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